

Evaluation on Characteristics and Family Structure of Juveniles Driven to Crime

Assoc. Professor Kürsat Şahin YILDIRIMER

St. Clements University Vice Dean and Lecturer;

Hüseyin GÜNEŞ, PhD

To cite this article: Hüseyin GÜNEŞ Science, Volume 4, No. 8-5, 2022, p. 538 – 558. - 0099-0001-2208-03015.

Our studies are in a format accredited, approved, and supported by EAALS - European Academic Studies and Laboratory Services. EAALS offers all our works, services, and publications to the world scientists at the stage of carrying our control, accreditation, and support processes to the international platform. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies -Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

ISSN: 2667-9515

Barcode: 977266795001

Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Dr. Ugur Ugural

Niyaz Bokvadze

Prof. Sabrina Corbi

Prof. Samantha Lewes

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

"• Current Science Multidisciplinary Academic Journal with Review Panel is a monthly multidisciplinary academic" ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

journal with a multi-science peer-review." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

• The magazine is published monthly.

"The magazine will be at the subscriber's address in the first week of the month." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia")

- The journal continues to be included in all international rankings and registrations. Quality articles and publications accelerate this ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") process. ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

- Response or rejection time for applications varies between 30 and 90 days." ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies – Current Science Georgia") ("Scientific Studies - Current Science Georgia")

Abstract

The number of juvenile delinquents is increasing day by day. Crimes committed by children continue to be an important problem in the world and in our country. Numerous studies have been conducted to determine the reasons that push children to commit crime. Studies conducted on juvenile delinquents indicate that the child tends towards delinquent behavior as a result of the combination of the negative aspects of individual, familial and social factors. Knowing the causes of juvenile delinquency and determining the measures to be taken in this context are important in terms of preventing juvenile delinquency and reintegrating children involved in crime into society. In this study, the characteristics and family structures of the children dragged into crime were evaluated. Within the scope of the study, firstly, the phenomenon of juvenile delinquent was discussed. Then, juvenile delinquency has been examined under the headings of gender, ethnic identity, social class and poverty, substance use and habits, mental illnesses, intelligence, early work, school and education status, peer group and peer abuse, street children, immigration and familial factors. reasons were evaluated.

Keywords: *Evaluation of Crime, Family Structure, Juveniles Driven, Crime, Family and Children*

1. Introduction

In the world and in Turkey, the facts of security, crime and victimization are parts of social reality. Security rights, as one of the most fundamental rights of individuals, are recognized in Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights and Article 1 of the European Declaration of Urban Rights. Despite these universal agreements, being a possible victim or

perpetrator of crime is the common reality of all humanity, and children are included as victims and perpetrators.

Juvenile delinquency, which has been a common problem of all nations throughout history, still maintains its currency today. Juvenile delinquency is defined as an individual who has not completed the age of 18, performing behaviours that are considered a crime according to the law (Akbaş et al., 2020). In studies conducted in our country, it is stated that children between the ages of 14-15 are most frequently involved in crime and the most common type of crime is theft (Şişmanlar et al., 2008). These children involved in crime are referred to as “children dragged into crime” in our laws (Child Protection Law).

Studies conducted on juvenile delinquents indicate that the child tends towards delinquent behaviour as a result of the combination of the negative aspects of individual, familial and social factors (Altun et al., 2016). Among these reasons that push the child to commit crime, there are factors such as low financial situation, lack of education, unsuitable friends and close environment, substance abuse, negative attitudes and behaviours of parents, migration (Şişmanlar et al., 2008; Akbaş et al., 2020).

The child learns and adopts these behaviors by imitating the positive or negative behaviors of the individuals in his social environment. For this reason, the family environment, in which social behaviors, value judgments and personality traits are laid, has an important place in the development of the child (Arıkan, 2020). Low education level of the parents, low income level of the family, having many children in the family, broken family structure, negative attitudes and behaviors of the parents towards each other and the child, the presence of individuals who have committed a crime or are prone to commit crimes in the family are seen as important risk factors in revealing the criminal behavior in the child (Amodei and Scott, 2002). At the same time, peer groups, especially acquired during adolescence, have a significant impact on the personality and behavior of the child (Sarı & Arslantaş, 2019). The environmental conditions and living standards of children working on the street cause them to develop adjustment disorders and different behavioral disorders, increasing their likelihood of committing crime. In studies, it is stated that mental illnesses such as substance use disorder, attention deficit and hyperactivity disorder (DHEB) and conduct disorder are important factors in criminal behavior, and low intelligence causes impulsivity and predisposes to committing crimes and recidivism

at an early age (Sittner & Hautala, 2016; Underwood and Washington, 2016; Demir and Bademci, 2016; Blanckstein et al., 2019).

Knowing the causes of juvenile delinquency and determining the measures to be taken in this context are important in terms of preventing juvenile delinquency and reintegrating children involved in crime into society (Şireli et al., 2014).

In this study, the characteristics and family structures of the children dragged into crime were evaluated.

2. The Case Of The Child Driven To Crime

In the Turkish legal system, every individual is a child until the age of eighteen, and children fall under the scope of criminal responsibility from the age of twelve. It is important how the child who commits any criminal act from the age of twelve is defined legally and socially. Phenomenology deals with the meaning given to phenomena. In this study, which is carried out with a phenomenological perspective, it is important what name the child and crime phenomenon are called together, how it is conceptualized and what this conceptualization means. From a universal perspective, the Beijing Rules (1985), which is included in the United Nations international juvenile legislation, is an internationally accepted declaration that also includes definitions on juvenile delinquency and prosecution. In this declaration, a child is defined as “a minor or juvenile who, under the relevant legal systems, is treated differently from adults in connection with committing a crime”. According to the Beijing Rules, a crime is any act that is punishable by law under the relevant legal systems. A juvenile delinquent is “a minor or young person who is found to have committed a crime or alleged to have committed a crime.” In this international document, the child is defined as “criminal”. The term "juvenile offender" (Turkish for juvenile delinquent) is used in the English version of this declaration. In the same way, the words juvenile (child in Turkish) and offender (criminal in Turkish) were used together. The English word “juvenile” means “child, young, not yet adult” and the expression “child” is used as its equivalent in the Turkish legal system. From a phenomenological point of view, the conceptualization of "juvenile delinquency" labels this age group as "delinquent", which is legally defined as juveniles and whose relationships with delinquency are treated

differently from adults. A child is still not a completely independent individual, even if he/she commits a legally criminal act. In this respect, if there is a criminal act, the child is the perpetrator of this crime, but socially, the child is also a victim in the axis of this criminal act. For these reasons, the expression "juvenile delinquency" is more preferred today to describe criminal acts involving children. The phrase "juvenile delinquent" is limiting. This expression is only a concept that shows the result of the action and ignores the social processes involved in this action. The expression "child delinquent", on the other hand, includes the assumption that the child is not an adult yet and that there may be social processes that lead him to commit a crime. The Turkish legal system also uses the term "child delinquent".

3. Factors Causing Juvenile Delinquency

Gender

There is a gender difference in the crime rate of children. Boys are more prone to commit crimes than girls. For example, the proportion of people under the age of 18 in the US is 25% of the total population. The rate of children arrested for any crime is 13%. The majority of these children are boys. Juvenile delinquency in America is mostly a male child issue. Nine out of ten children arrested for more serious crimes such as murder, rape, robbery, carrying a gun, sexual crimes and gambling are boys (Regoli, Hewitt, Delisi, 2014: 54-58). Chesney-Lind and Chagnon (2015:103-120), who criticize the fact that delinquency studies are mostly conducted on boys, argue that the victim roles of girls in delinquency are neglected. According to feminist theory, crime studies should be theorized within the framework of gender equality rather than the already dominant sexism.

There are social reasons for the low number of girls dragged into crime in the overall rate of being dragged into crime. For example, a study of young people from 11 European countries and from different ethnic groups (Junger-Tas, Ribeaud, & Cruyff, 2004) showed that there is a significant difference in delinquency between girls and boys, and that delinquency is higher in boys. It was found that the effect of social control originating from family and school on delinquency was similar in boys and girls. The reason for the difference in delinquency rates between boys and girls is the tighter social control over girls (Junger-Tas, Ribeaud, & Cruyff,

2004). This study was conducted with girls and boys and showed the effect of gender-based social control on delinquency in the social process. However, studies on delinquency do not always take into account the gender factor.

Studies with both boys and girls in the crime literature are few in number. Bircan and Bacanlı (2005) measured the criminal behavior of equal numbers of girls and boys attending high school with a 35-question “criminal behavior scale”. The purpose of the questions is to determine “the behaviors among adolescents that are not reflected in official institutions, but would be considered as crimes if they were caught and would bring them against the law” (Bircan and Bacanlı, 2005: 69). In this study, it was determined that the criminal behavior scores of the adolescents differed significantly in favor of the girls (Bircan & Bacanlı, 2005: 61).

It is known that boys tend to commit criminal behavior more than girls, and this is due to social control mechanisms and gender-related social role expectations. (Bircan and Bacanlı, 2005:76). One of the many studies to support this information on crime and gender was carried out in a correctional facility in India where delinquent juveniles were found. In this reformatory, the number of boys (126 people) who committed crimes is more than girls (42 people). 73.57% of the girls are over the age of 16. It has been observed that crimes after the age of sixteen for both girls and boys are mostly violent crimes (such as murder, rape, assault) and there is no significant gender differentiation in this regard. The crimes committed by girls starting from the age of sixteen are mostly more violent crimes such as murder and assault. Before the age of 16, crimes such as theft are common among girls.

In summary, the majority of children driven into crime are boys. Criminal studies are also mostly done with boys. Studies conducted with girls and boys show that girls' crime tendencies are lower than boys. Serious crimes such as murder involving girls can be linked to tensions with spouses and relatives. The excess of social control over girls is another result of crime studies.

Ethnicity, social class and poverty

Some of the decriminalization studies provide information on ethnic differences, social structure differences, and the relationship between poverty and delinquency. Factors such as ethnic identity and social class, which are statistically correlated with crime rates, are identified. But there are also underlying social reasons for this situation. Various factors, from the legal definition of crime to the approach of security units to crime and criminals, can cause a certain social group to be labeled as a criminal. In this section, the findings of delinquency studies on ethnic identity, social class and poverty are included.

Within every society, there are one or more ethnic groups associated with crime in public perception. However, exposure to crime usually occurs within the same group, not between ethnic groups. For example, there are forensic records and studies showing that black Americans and Hispanics (Latin American) are more effective in both falling victim to a crime and committing a crime than whites. However, this situation is related to the fact that these groups are open to risk environments related to poverty, family disintegration and cultural factors rather than race and ethnic identity (Regoli, Hewitt, Delisi, 2014).

According to statistics in official records in the USA, it is seen that African-Americans are more involved in judicial proceedings and convictions than their own population. However, according to studies using the self-report method, it was revealed that there was no significant difference between whites and African-Americans in terms of crime frequency and prevalence, and the difference changed in favor of whites in terms of arrest and conviction. The underlying reasons for the undisciplined behavior or involvement of children in ethnic groups are social characteristics and racial prejudices (Bartollas & Schmallegger, 2017). Young people belonging to a certain racial or ethnic minority are more present in the US juvenile justice system. Compared to whites, the fact that these children are black and Hispanic adversely affects the outcome of the case. Attempts to prevent or reduce racial inequality in the juvenile justice system have not been effective (Leiber and Fix, 2019).

The approach of the police in crimes involving children determines whether the situation of the child group in question will be considered as a crime. The police are considered to be less tolerant, especially towards children belonging to ethnic groups and minority groups. Thus, while incidents involving children in minority groups due to racial and ethnic identity are recorded as crimes, there is a perception that some crimes involving children outside these

groups are ignored. Police are seen as people who arrest some children or ignore some crimes. In order to change this perception, solutions such as bringing the children involved in petty crimes to a center where social workers and mental health specialists are located were considered. However, police-citizen interaction can also have unexpected negative consequences. The negative consequences of police arrests and detentions are often universal, given the police response to white and black youth. However, compared to white youth, black youth experience higher levels of contact with the police and are less satisfied with the police's approach. How this process is shaped by race and ethnicity is important because the overall impact of police-initiated contact on young people is still disproportionate and against blacks (Slocum and Wiley, 2018).

When looking at the relationship between socioeconomic status and delinquency, there is little data that shows that crime is specifically a lower-class act. According to studies, when it comes to minor crimes such as insults and curfew violations, there is no significant class difference among young people in terms of crime frequency and number. While there is no difference in the prevalence of crime among children and youth from different socio-economic classes, lower-class children and youth are more likely to face the judicial system in terms of being arrested and appearing in juvenile court (Bartollas & Schmalleger, 2017).

If ethnic minorities lack economic resources, they find themselves in an insecure and disadvantaged situation against the outside world. 70% of black children are born in their teens and to unmarried parents. It is a serious problem that the 'father role model' in the family, which is a factor that reduces the delinquency of children, is not present in such disintegrated families. Although the issue of juvenile delinquency is perceived as a 'big city' problem, comparative studies of urban and rural areas show that family variables are significantly associated with juvenile delinquency everywhere. Life experiences related to disadvantaged family environments may cause children in the mentioned ethnic group to adopt an insecure and aggressive attitude towards society and its values. Similarly, in the relationship between social class and juvenile delinquency, those who commit the most violent crimes such as murder, armed robbery and rape have a history of poverty (Regoli, Hewitt, Delisi, 2014).

In summary, the contact of persons belonging to a racial or ethnic group with crime may be higher than forensic records. In the case of the USA, the fact that blacks have higher criminal

records than whites is explained by the police's approach to blacks. Sociologically, delinquency is related to the fact that these groups are in a social class that is open to social risk factors such as immigration, family dissolution, and poverty, rather than race and ethnic group. The behavior of children born to these conditions is shaped by the social disadvantages and unconventional opportunities they are exposed to. The social environment and network of relationships formed within the lives shaped by social class and poverty may distract the child from legal goals. Especially communication with peers and how they spend time together are the determinants of behaviors in childhood and adolescence. The child learns to commit crime in his social environment.

Substance use and habits

Goldstein emphasized that substance use causes situations such as excitement, anger, and paranoia in the person, and that violent behavior may occur as a result of the use of some substances. These substances, which increase the intensity of emotion as a result of changes in the body and cause weakening in consciousness and behavioral control, can lead the person to criminal behavior. Individuals may resort to any means to obtain this substance, and when they cannot obtain it, they may become involved in crime by reacting with anger and violence (Arabacı et al., 2017).

Mental Illnesses

It has been reported that most of the children involved in crime have one or more accompanying psychiatric diseases, and the most common psychiatric diseases in these children are ADHD, oppositional defiance and behavior disorder, depression, anxiety disorder and mental retardation. Self-harming behavior and recidivism are also common in these individuals]. In addition to these disorders, other mental disorders that have been shown to be associated with delinquent/deviant behavior in children and adolescents are mood disorder and post-traumatic stress disorder. It is also reported that traumas such as domestic violence, abuse and neglect

experienced by the child are quite common among children involved in crime (Schubert et al., 2011; Eyüboğlu and Eyüboğlu, 2018).

4. Intelligence

It is thought that having a low intelligence level causes cognitive and behavioral impulsivity, and these children tend to more delinquent behavior. At the same time, it is stated that children with low intelligence can enter into a depressive mood caused by low achievement and this situation makes them a more risky group in terms of involvement in crime (Korkmaz & Erden, 2010).

Obligation to work at an early age

A substantial proportion of children in the world may have to work from an early age due to financial reasons. This situation can negatively affect the school success of children and cause them not to complete their education. The environments in which children work are generally unhealthy, unsafe and prevent their physical, mental and moral development. These children, who are away from family and school supervision, can acquire bad habits such as cigarettes, alcohol and drugs, but they can exhibit negative behaviors and turn to crime by taking deviant behaviors in and around the workplace as role models (Bağış, 2019).

5. School and Education Status

The education-teaching process is an important element in the formation of the individual's relationship and behavior and in the completion of the socialization of the individual. In addition, education functions as a social solution in traditional communities that have adopted the elements of violence (Arabacı & Taş, 2017). Any disruption or inability to complete this process will negatively affect the child's development, psychology and adaptation. Inadequate education may cause insufficient socialization in children, leading them to turn to criminal behavior. As a result, negative behaviors such as absenteeism from school, truancy, disciplinary

punishment, and theft can be seen in the child. It is known that low school success also has a reinforcing effect in terms of repeating criminal behavior (Arabacı & Taş, 2017).

Peer Group

Studies report that peers who commit crimes are a very important factor in the juvenile's tendency to commit crime (Arabacı & Taş, 2017). The child adopts and tries to apply the behaviors and actions of his friends at the highest level in order to be respected and accepted by his friends. Even if the child finds the attitude of the group of friends wrong, he has to comply with them in order not to be excluded from the group. Children who receive insufficient attention and control by their parents are more affected by the antisocial attitudes and behaviors of their friend groups. Children who have a tendency to or have been involved in criminal behavior are more vulnerable to the negative behavior of their peer group (Aalsma et al., 2015).

Peer Abuse

Peer abuse is the continuous and repetitive systematic harming and hurtful aggressive behavior of one or a group of children to a child of the same age group, and is often seen as bullying/bullying behaviors. Negative peer relations may cause the child's aggressive behavior to increase or the children who are under pressure by their peers to commit crimes, to get involved in crime. Studies have also reported that there is a significant relationship between peer abuse and involvement in crime (Karataş, 2020).

6. Street children/Children living on the street

There are many risk factors that cause most of the children, who have low quality of life in many aspects and lead a life with limited opportunities, to turn to criminal behavior in their living conditions. For a number of reasons, children who spend most of their lives on the streets are known as "street children". These children face all the negative situations and dangers on the street, and they become prone to guilt over time. These children, who generally adopt

harmful habits and live in groups, frequently suffer from drug use and selling, harassing others by harassing them, begging, theft, extortion and murder, and psychological problems (Aalsma et al., 2015).

7. Migration

Migration causes unemployment and poverty in cities as a result of increasing population, but it can also reinforce the negative behaviors of children by causing social and cultural adaptation problems (Korkmaz & Erden, 2010). Studies conducted on juvenile delinquents indicate that there are conflicts between social classes, social tensions, and an increase in juvenile delinquency, especially theft, in regions where immigration and slums occur (Gönültaş and Hilal, 2012).

8. Familial Factors

The first environment in which the child socializes is the family. The foundation of personality traits is laid in the family environment where the individual lives together since birth, and the child takes family members as role models. For this reason, family structure is one of the most important risk factors for delinquency. In this context, situations such as crowded family, domestic violence, broken family, weak family commitment, over-tolerant or over-pressing parents, low income level of the family appear as risk factors for the child's negative behaviors (Arabacı & Taş, 2017).

It is reported that the majority of the children involved in crime are the children of broken families, and especially the divorce of the parents increases the risk of the child turning to criminal behavior (Arabacı and Taş, 2017).

The size of the family is mostly related to the number of children the family has. In families with many children, the social, emotional and economic opportunities of the children are much less, and at the same time, the interest and support of the parents is less. As a result, inadequacy in the development and supervision of the child arises. Juveniles whose necessary needs cannot

be met may be more exposed to risk factors that lead them to delinquent behavior (Yavuzer, 1981).

The sociocultural and economic level of the family has also been found to be effective factors for delinquency in studies. It is reported that the families of the children involved in crime mostly have a low income level and the education level of their parents, especially the education level of the mother, is low (Acar et al., 2015).

The presence of criminals in the family, neglect and abuse of the child are also reported as risk factors for juvenile delinquency (Çakaloz et al., 2016). Since the child will learn by imitating many behaviors and attitudes, the presence of individuals who have committed crimes in the family is an important factor. The child, who learns the concept of crime from the lifestyle of his family with whom he lives, can apply this crime behavior in the future by adopting it (Güneş & Gökler, 2017).

Studies show that children who grow up in families with insufficient parental love and care tend to commit crime. Many factors such as the negative attitude of the parents towards the child, insufficient supervision of the child, lack of communication and conflicts with the child have negative effects on the child's development and pave the way for the child to turn to criminal behavior (Güneş & Gökler, 2017).

Childhood in human life is a developmental period that is mostly shaped by family relationships. The family is a sociological structure that prepares the individual for life and ensures his socialization. However, this social unit in which the individual is born and gains basic cultural values does not always offer positive experiences. For this reason, the family is one of the living areas where being driven into crime is associated. In this section, the results of delinquency studies on family are discussed.

At the Cambridge Crime Investigation, 411 London-born men were interviewed nine times between the ages of eight and forty-six, eight of which were attended by their families. According to this long-term study, these extreme behaviors of boys who showed the most antisocial behavior in their childhood continued into their adulthood. This situation of young chronic/repeat offenders has followed a similar pattern in their own children as a kind of inheritance or tradition. In this study, delinquent parent, delinquent sibling, harsh discipline,

poor supervision, parental conflict, large family and young mother were listed as familial risk factors for chronic juvenile delinquency (Farrington and West 1990).

In the studies conducted in Turkey, socio-demographic characteristics of the families of the children driven to crime show similarity. Studies show that 60% or more of the children driven to crime are alive and married. It has been determined that the majority of the children dragged into crime have 3-4 siblings and live in crowded families. Parents' education level is low. The parents of the delinquent child are mostly primary school graduates (Erdoğan, 2010; Güneş and Gökler, 2017; Şahiner, 2010; Yavuzer, 2018). For example, in a sociological study in which factors correlated with delinquency were tested (Avcı, 2009), the forms of a sample group of 1399 persons under the age of 18, who came/ brought to the Children's Branch in Erzurum in 2005-2006 and were kept a "Child Information Form", were statistically analyzed. analyzes were applied. According to this result, the child's educational status, employment status, immigration status, family-relative-environment relations have an effect on delinquency. In addition, the absence of a mother or father and the place where the child lives (family, relatives, dormitory, boarding school, etc.) have no effect on delinquency; It has been determined that the current age period has an effect on the type of crime committed (Avcı, 2009:176).

The characteristics of the parents and the bond they establish with their children are decisive in being dragged into crime. For example, as the education level of the parents increases, the rate of adolescents' involvement in crime decreases. According to the education level of the parents, their attitudes and behaviors about raising children also change. A child spends most of his life with his family. Children who grow up with educated parents learn to show a positive approach in coping with the problem in the family (Akduman et al., 2007:156-161). In addition, the guidance and supervision provided by the parents to their children is a determining factor in delinquency. Situations that lead to poor parental guidance and supervision are seen as risk factors for juvenile delinquency (Petrosino et al., 2009; Tyler et al., 2008). For example, Rathinabalan and Naaraayan (2017) identified high father's age (over 50 years old), father's smoking, mother's work and single parenthood as familial risk factors that reduce supervision and guidance on the child. In summary, factors such as inadequate communication within the family, familial characteristics leading to poor supervision, and low education level of parents are among familial risk factors for delinquency.

The attitude of the parent to the child and the approach to the problems that occur are effective on the behavior of the child. In a study investigating the parenting style of black, Hispanic and white mothers, it was found that strict authoritarian parenting had the least deterrent effect on delinquency in all three groups. Maternal indifference is associated with delinquency only for Caucasian children. The same is not true for blacks and Hispanics. In all three groups, the rate of delinquency of children who describe their mothers as harsh authoritative is higher than those who describe their mother as authoritative. Strict authoritarian parenting is the most ineffective at preventing delinquency. Parental support is the biggest factor in reducing the rates of delinquency (Mowen & Schroeder, 2015).

The family environment is a structure that contains both risk and protective factors for the child at the same time. It is reported that a child exposed to six or more risk factors is ten times more likely to commit violence in childhood compared to a child exposed to only one risk factor (Herrenkohl et al., 2000). While risk factors within the family will lead a child to delinquency or antisocial behavior, protective factors can change the child's life course. For example, a child who has been harmed by one of the family members can be protected by another family member. In his autobiographical work, Knausgaard (2016, p. 269) says, "He saved me because without him, I would have spent my childhood alone with my father and sooner or later I would have killed myself in one way or another. But my mother was there, balancing out my father's darkness." The child, who is helpless under the focus of risk and tension in his life, may turn away from the family and seek meaning in uncontrolled friend groups as the next step.

The communication pattern in the family has a relationship with the delinquency of children. Functional communication is open, tolerant, guiding and effective. This communication pattern enables the child to gain a positive sense of self. Dysfunctional communication causes an uneasy family environment. In this case, it becomes difficult for the child to develop a positive self-perception and the child cannot manage the negative environmental impact. Delinquency rate is high in families with dysfunctional communication. Delinquency of divorced parents and sons is highly correlated. The reason for this is that the child living with a single parent is deprived of the functional communication environment in the family (Thoyibah et al., 2017).

In the United States in the 19th century, a group called Child Savers, who advocated that every child is inherently good, adopted the idea that juvenile delinquency was due to external factors

such as poverty, immigration and inadequate parental guidance, and as a solution, they removed the problem children from bad family conditions. They offered placement in remedial settings. It is this group that is responsible for establishing juvenile courts and shelters. It has been observed that the initial goal of 'protecting children from crime' of the New York Shelter, which was opened as the first of its kind in the USA in 1825, turned into 'protecting the society from children'. The child, who was taken from poverty and similar bad conditions, faced other problems in the shelters, the children became 'without an identity'. Socializing within the family and the natural social environment is a process that gives the child an identity. Children staying in shelters are deprived of this opportunity. In the continuation of various social criticisms, as a result of the search for new solutions to prevent juvenile delinquency, the Juvenile Court was established in Illinois in 1899. Unlike previous solutions, it is aimed to supervise children not in different institutions, but within the home and community to which the child belongs (Regoli, Hewitt and Delisi, 2014:13-17). It is seen that the family is the primary and most important institution for the development of the child. For this reason, one of the subjects that researches on delinquency focus on is the characteristics of the child's family.

A study comparing the family-focused studies on the reasons for delinquency of children in Turkey (Kayma Güneş & Gökler, 2017) states that delinquency is handled with the structural and qualitative characteristics of the family. Structural features include the number of children, the breakdown of the family, and the presence of a criminal in the family. Qualitative characteristics, on the other hand, consist of factors such as parenting style and family communication. According to the studies summarized in this study, delinquent children generally come from families with four or more children. There is an indirect relationship between divorce and single parent and delinquency. In cases where this situation is not managed well, if family satisfaction, communication and surveillance decrease, the delinquency increases. When we look at the family structures of the children driven to crime, most of the parents are married. Delinquency is related to the inadequacy of communication within the family rather than family integrity. The parents of the majority of delinquent children have an education level of primary school or below. The education level of mothers is lower than that of honeymooners. More than half of the children dragged into crime have a criminal in their family (Güneş and Gökler, 2017).

In summary, family delinquency is a subject that is handled in different dimensions in studies. The family is an area where many problems are solved and care and guidance are carried out for the child. In addition, the family environment, with its structural and qualitative characteristics, also includes processes that may lead to delinquency. Factors such as effective communication within the family, competent parenting, and high socio-economic level are protective against delinquency. All kinds of structural and qualitative characteristics that reduce communication, supervision and care within the family and low socioeconomic status are risk factors for delinquency. Familial characteristics are closely related to the ethnic identity, social class and socio-economic level to which the family belongs in the macro dimension.

9. Conclusion

The subject of juvenile delinquency occupies a wide place in criminal studies. In the crime literature, where quantitative studies are dominant, data on the causes of delinquency are mostly reached. This information is not comprehensive for the experience and process of each child driven to crime. For example, although annual statistics show an increase in the rate of juvenile delinquency, it cannot be understood how children are involved in crime at a higher rate. The most important institutions in the socialization of a child are primarily the family and the school in his later life. Improvements related to these two factors will prevent the child from repeating negative behaviors and negative behaviors. In this context, our recommendations are as follows; Every woman who is found to be pregnant should be given guidance and counseling services by the relevant institutions so that she can give birth to a mentally healthy child. The continuity of this education given to the family should be ensured with the meetings organized by the health units (family doctor, public health) that take an active role in the follow-up of the pregnancy and the baby after the baby is born, and the school administration when the education and training life of the child begins. Establishing family psychosocial assistance units, following up families and children residing in sociodemographically prone to delinquency regions, providing counseling services for children and families in families where individuals with substance abuse and domestic violence are common, and the best interests of the child. It is necessary to implement social service programs by taking into account the need to maintain the implementation of all these applications by supervising them. In our country, youth centers

are established in order to enable young people to make use of their free time in line with their interests, desires and abilities, to direct them to social, cultural, artistic and sportive activities, to enable them to participate as beneficial citizens in the society, and to carry out studies to protect young people from harmful habits. Increasing the number of these centers and informing all families about the centers, especially those living in risky areas with low socioeconomic status and people involved in crime, promoting these centers in a way that will attract the attention of children, ensuring that all children reach youth centers by providing financial support, if necessary, protecting children from dangerous environments they may encounter outside. It will be useful in preventing them from turning to negative actions and behaviors. The failure to provide care for the child due to economic reasons, the failure to meet his needs, and the disruptions in education are important factors that push the child to commit crime. It is necessary to develop and implement economic and social policies so that the education of the child is not affected by the financial difficulties of the family. In this context, in addition to providing financial assistance to families with low income, it would be beneficial to offer job opportunities in that field by providing vocational training to people who are responsible for taking care of the child. It is very important to observe the children who spend most of the day at school by the school administration, especially the classroom teachers and guidance teachers, to identify the children who are prone to commit criminal behavior and to rehabilitate these children in cooperation with the relevant institutions and families, in terms of raising them as useful individuals for the society. For this reason, all educators should be trained on children driven to crime. It is an important factor to ensure that the child can gain communication skills, socialize in a healthy way, and keep the child away from dangerous environments that push him to crime. Organizing programs in schools that include activities that will increase children's interest in school, apart from lessons, and ensuring that all children participate in these activities will be beneficial in school attendance by increasing the child's love of school and increasing his commitment to school. Investigating the reasons for the failure of children with low academic success, creating supportive projects for these children, and providing the necessary psychological support by the guidance teacher, ensuring that the children are checked by an expert by interviewing their families will prevent the child from leaving school and becoming exposed to external dangers. Directing the children working on the street, who do not have formal education, to vocational training and ensuring that they work in a safe work environment that is more appropriate for their age after the training they receive will prevent them from being

involved in crime by keeping them away from environments that may adversely affect their behavior as well as their economic well-being.

Violent series and news broadcast on television, computer games that won awards as a result of violence have an important place in children's tendency to violent crimes. Children's access to such publications or games should be restricted.

The application of necessary counseling and other measures to the families of the children who have been rehabilitated with a protective measure decision will prevent the child from returning to the same negative conditions and turning to crime again.

As a result, it is very important to carry out treatment and follow-up for the identified risk factors of the juvenile delinquents, to take the necessary protective and supportive measures, and to monitor whether these measures are implemented by the administrative institutions or whether they are sufficient. In order for these children driven to crime to live in harmony with society, necessary economic, social and cultural arrangements should be made.

10. References

Aalsma MC, White LM, Lau KS, Perkins A, Monahan P, Grisso T. (2015). Behavioral Health Care Needs, Detention Based Care, and Criminal Recidivism at Community Reentry From Juvenile Detention: A Multisite Survival Curve Analysis. *Am J Public Health*, 105:1372-1378.

Acar G, Demir A, Görmez D, Keser İ. (2015). Aile Ve Çocuk Suçluluğu İlişkisi. *Hacettepe Üniversitesi Sağlık Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi*, 1-13

Akbaş, G. E., Karataş, K., & Orhan, M. G. (2020). Ankara'da Çocuk Suçluluğu: Emniyet Çocuk Şubeye Gelen Olgular Üzerinden Bir Değerlendirme. *Türkiye Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 24(1), 137-156.

Akduman, G. G., Akduman, B. ve Cantürk, G. (2007). Ergen suçluluğunda

bazı kişisel ve ailesel özelliklerin incelenmesi. *Türk Pediatri Arş.* 42(4): 156-161

Altun H, Şahin N, Fındıklı E, Sınır H. (2016). Suça sürüklenen çocukların suç tipleri, sosyodemografik ve klinik özellikleri. *Adli Tıp Dergisi*. 30(3):196-204

Amodei N, Scott AA. (2002). Psychologists' contribution to the prevention of youth violence. *Soc Sci J*, 39:511-526

Arabacı LB, Taş G, Dikeç G. (2017). Çocuk ve Ergenlerde Madde Kullanımı, Suça Yönelme, Ruhsal Bozukluklar ve Hemşirelik Bakımı. *Bağımlılık Dergisi*, 18(4):135-144

Arabacı LB, Taş G. (2017). Çocuklarda Suça Sürükleyen Faktörler, Ruhsal Problemler ve Hemşirelik Bakımı.

Journal of Psychiatric Nursing, 8(2):110–117

Arıkan, H. (2020). Türkiye’de Çevresel Etmenler, Yoksulluk ve Çocuk Suçluluğu Haritalama. *Kırıkkale Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 10(1), 53-78.

Avcı, M. (2009). *Çocuk Suçluluğunun Toplumsal Nedenleri*. (Erzurum ili Örneği). Yayınlanmamış doktora tezi. Erzurum: Erzurum Üniversitesi, Adli Tıp Enstitüsü

Bağış RC. (2019). Çocukları Suça Sürükleyen Çevresel Nedenler: Sosyal Bağ Ve Sosyal Öğrenme Teorileri Işığında Bir Değerlendirme. *Humanitas Uluslararası Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 7 (14): 203-221

Bartollas, C. ve Schmallegger, F. (2017). *Çocuk Suçluluğu* (çev: D. Yücel ve M. B. Gönültaş). Ankara: Nobel Yay.

Bircan, S. ve Bacanlı, F. (2005). Ergenlerin Duygusal Zekalarının Çatışma Eğilimlerine Ve Suç Davranışlarına Etkisi. *M.Ü. Atatürk Eğitim Fakültesi Eğitim Bilimleri Dergisi*, Sayı 22:61-82

Blanckstein, A., van der Rijcken, R., Eeren, H. V., Lange, A., Scholte, R., Moonen, X., ... & Didden, R. (2019). Evaluating the effects of multisystemic therapy for adolescents with intellectual disabilities and antisocial or delinquent behaviour and their parents. *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, 32(3), 575-590.

Çakaloz B, Ünlü G, Terzioğlu MA, Kapubağlı N, Tekkanat Ç. (2016). Çocuklarda suç davranışı ile sosyodemografik özelliklerin ve zekanın ilişkisi. *Anadolu Psikiyatri Dergisi*, 17(5).

Chesney-Lind, M. and Chagnon, N. (2015). Gender, Delinquency, and Youth Justice: Issues for a Global Century. (ed. Marvin D. Krohn and Jodi Lane). In. *The Handbook of Juvenile Delinquency and Juvenile Justice*. (103-120). UK: Wiley Blackwell

Çocuk Koruma Kanunu. Erişim adresi:

<https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/MevzuatMetin/1.5.5395.pdf>

Demir, M., & Bademci, H. Ö. (2016). Suça Sürüklenmiş Bir Gencin Bakış Açısıyla Çocuk Suçluluğu: Olgu Sunumu/Juvenile Delinquency from the Perspective of a Juvenile Pushed to Crime: Case Report. *Atatürk Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 20(1).

Erdoğan, F. (2010). *Kanunla İhtilafa Düşmüş Çocuklar ve Çocuk Suçluluğuna Etki Eden Sosyo-Ekonomik Faktörler*. Yayınlanmamış yüksek lisans tezi. İstanbul: İstanbul Üniversitesi, Adli Tıp Enstitüsü

Eyüboğlu M., Eyüboğlu D. (2018). Suça Sürüklenen Çocuklarda Psikiyatrik Bozukluklar, Sosyodemografik Özellikler ve Risk Faktörleri. *Klinik Psikiyatri*, 21:7-14

Farrington D.P., West D.J. (1990) The Cambridge Study in Delinquent Development: A Long-Term Follow-Up of 411 London Males. In: Kerner HJ., Kaiser G. (eds) *Kriminalität*. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg

Gönültaş BM, Hilal A. (2012). Çocuk Suçluluğunda Göç Faktörü: Adana Örneği. *J For Med*, 26(3):156-64

Güneş DK, Gökler R. (2017). Türkiye' de Suça Sürüklenen Çocukların Aile Özellikleri. *Uluslararası İnsan Bilimleri Dergisi*, 14(4):3742-3755

Herrenkohl, T. L., Maguin, E., Hill, K. G., Hawkins, J. D., Abbott, R. D. ve Catalano, R. F. (2000). Developmental risk factors for youth violence. *J Adol Health*. 26(7): 176-186.

Junger-Tas, J., Ribeaud, D., and Cruyff, M. J. L. F. (2004). Juvenile Delinquency and Gender. *European Journal of Criminology*, 1(3), 333–375

Karataş, S. (2020). Suça Sürüklenen Çocuklar ve Suç Mağduru Çocuklara Yönelik Bir Değerlendirme. *Psikiyatride Güncel Yaklaşımlar*, 12(4), 575-586.

Korkmaz MN, Erden G. (2010). Çocukları suç davranışına yönelten olası risk faktörleri. *Türk Psikoloji Yazıları*. 13(25):76-87.

Leiber, M. J. and Fix, R. (2019) Reflections on the Impact of Race and Ethnicity on Juvenile Court Outcomes and Efforts to Enact Change. *American Journal of Criminal Justice*. 44: 581–608

Mowen, T. J., ve Schroeder, R. D. (2015). Maternal Parenting Style and Delinquency by Race and the Moderating Effect of Structural Disadvantage. *Youth and Society*. 50(2):139-159

Petrosino, A., Derzon, J., & Lavenberg, J. (2009). The role of the family in crime and delinquency: Evidence from prior quantitative reviews, *Southwest Journal of Criminal Justice*, 6 (2), 108–132

Rathinabalan, I., Naaraayan, S.A. (2017) Effect of family factors on juvenile delinquency. *Int J Contemp Pediatr*. 4 (6): 2079-2082

Regoli, R. M., Hewitt, J. D. and M. Delisi (2014). *Delinquency in Society*. USA: Jones and Bartlett Learning

Şahiner, D. S. (2010). *Uyuşturucu Madde Kullanmak Suçu ile Denetimli Serbestlik Tedbiri Alan Kişilerin Sosyodemografik Özelliklerinin ve Rorschach Kişilik Testi Yanıtlarının Taranması*. Yayınlanmamış doktora tezi. İstanbul: İstanbul Üniversitesi, Adli Tıp Enstitüsü

Sarı E, Arslantaş H. (2019). Lise Öğrencisi Ergenlerin Suça Yönelik Tutumları ve Risk Faktörleri. *Klinik Psikiyatri*, 22:71-82

Schubert CA, Mulvey EP, Glasheen C. (2011). Influence of mental health and substance use problems and criminogenic risk on outcomes in serious juvenile offenders. *J Am Acad Child Adolesc Psychiatry*.50(9):925-37.

Şireli Ö, Esenkaya Z, Yaylalı H, Uğur Ç, Duman NS, Gül B, Günay M, Kılıç HT, Gürkan CK, Kılıç BG. (2014). Suça Karışmış Ergenlerin Psikiyatrik

Değerlendirmesi: Olgu Serisi. *Çocuk ve Gençlik Ruh Sağlığı Dergisi*, 21(2):131-8

Şişmanlar ŞG, Biçer Ü, Coşkun A. (2008). Adli Psikiyatri. *Çocuk ve Ergen Psikiyatrisi Temel Kitabı*. FÇ Çetin, A Coşkun, E İşeri ve ark. (Ed), Ankara, Çocuk ve Gençlik Ruh Sağlığı Derneği 2008; 770-81.

Sittner, K. J., & Hautala, D. (2016). Aggressive delinquency among north american indigenous adolescents: trajectories and predictors. *Aggressive behavior*, 42(3), 274-286.

Slocum, L. A. and Wiley, S. A. (2018) “Experience Of The Expected?” Race and Ethnicity Differences In The Effects Of Police Contact On Youth. *American Society of Criminology*, 56(2):402–432

Thoyibah Z, Nurjannah I, Sumarni D. (2017). Correlation between family communication patterns and juvenile delinquency in junior high school. *Belitung Nursing Journal*. 3(4): 297-306

Tyler, K. A., Johnson, K. A., & Brownridge, D. A. (2008). A longitudinal study of the effects of child maltreatment on later outcomes among high-risk adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 37, 506–521

Underwood, L. A., & Washington, A. (2016). Mental illness and juvenile offenders. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 13(2), 228.

Yavuzer H. (1981). *Psikososyal Açıdan Çocuk Suçluluğu*. İstanbul: İstanbul Üniversitesi Eğitim Fakültesi Yayınları.

Yavuzer, H. (2018) *Çocuk ve Suç*.

18. Baskı. İstanbul: Remzi Kitabevi